

FRIEDEL AND CRAFTS ACETYLATION OF METHYL β -RESORCYLATE AND RESACETOPHENONE

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Methyl β -resorcybate has been acetylated under the conditions of the Friedel and Crafts reaction using acetic anhydride and acetyl chloride and the γ -isomer, methyl 2:4-dihydroxy-3-acetylbenzoate isolated for the first time. The structure has been proved by simultaneous hydrolysis and decarboxylation to 2-acetylresorcinol. The reaction has been studied using different proportions of the acetylating agent and aluminium chloride. β -Resorcylic acid has also been similarly acetylated. The acetylation of resacetophenone using different proportions of acetic anhydride and aluminium chloride has been studied and the procedure for the separation of 2:4-diacetylresorcinol from the 4:6-diacetylresorcinol described. 2:4:6-Triacetylresorcinol has also been obtained in an excellent yield.

Desai and Ekhtas (*Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1938, 8A, 194) and Desai and Radha (*ibid.*, 1940, 12A, 46) subjected methyl β -resorcybate (I) to the action of acetic anhydride in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride, and obtained only the β -substituted compound, methyl 2:4-dihydroxy-5-acetylbenzoate. No γ -isomer was isolated. It is now found that in the same reaction a considerable quantity of the hitherto unknown γ -isomer, methyl 2:4-dihydroxy-3-acetylbenzoate (II, R=Me) is also formed. This has been isolated and its structure established by hydrolysis and decarboxylation to the known 2-acetylresorcinol (III), previously prepared by Mauthner (*J. prakt. Chem.*, 1934, 139, 290) from 2:6-dimethoxybenzotrile and methylmagnesium iodide. Limaye (*Ber.*, 1934, 67, 12) has developed an elegant general method for the preparation of 2-acylresorcinols, by the hydrolysis of 7-hydroxy-4-methyl-8-acylcoumarins. Following this method Sugasawa (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 1483) prepared 2-acetylresorcinol by the hydrolysis of 7-hydroxy-4-methyl-8-acetylcoumarin. The ester (II, R=Me) could be directly converted into 2-acetylresorcinol in very good yield by heating with alkali. The ester was hydrolysed to the acid (II, R=H) by keeping in contact with cold alkali. The same acid was obtained by carboxylation of 2-acetylresorcinol with sodium bicarbonate in glycerine solution.

Several experiments were carried out with a view to increasing the yield of the γ -isomer, and it was found that the proportions of β - and γ -isomers varied depending on the quantity of acetic anhydride and aluminium chloride used in the reaction:

(1) With one mole of acetic anhydride and one of aluminium chloride to one of methyl β -resorcybate the yields of both the β - and the γ -isomers were low, a large quantity of methyl β -resorcybate remaining unreacted.

(2) With two moles of aluminium chloride the β - and the γ -isomers were obtained in almost equal proportions.

(3) With three moles of aluminium chloride, the γ -isomer was obtained in almost the same yield as in (2) but the β -isomer was obtained in a very good yield.

(4) When the reaction was carried out with two moles of acetic anhydride and three moles of aluminium chloride, the γ -isomer was formed in good yield but a very large quantity of the diacetyl derivative, methyl 2:4-dihydroxy-3:5-diacetylbenzoate, was also formed. Increase in the heating time to six hours or the temperature to 120°-130° did not lead to any appreciable increase in the yield of the γ -isomer.

At the end of the reaction the mixture in all cases was subjected to steam distillation. After the nitrobenzene distilled over the γ -isomer with a little of the β -isomer continued to distil. In experiments (2) and (3), the β - and the γ -isomers were separated from the mixture by fractionation with hexane or petroleum ether (b.p. 40°-60°). The γ -isomer is much more soluble than the β -isomer. In experiment (4) the γ -isomer could be obtained pure by a couple of crystallisations from alcohol. The diacetyl derivative does not come over with steam.

2-Acetylresorcinol could be directly obtained from the mixture of the two isomeric esters by hydrolysis with hot sodium hydroxide. A mixture of 2-acetylresorcinol and 2:4-dihydroxy-5-acetylbenzoic acid was obtained from which the constituents were separated by sodium bicarbonate solution.

Desai and Ekkhas (*loc. cit.*) have observed that acetyl chloride does not condense with methyl β -resorcyate at room temperature. It is now found that acetyl chloride condenses with methyl β -resorcyate when the reaction is carried out on a steam-bath. With one mole each of acetyl chloride and aluminium chloride the results were identical with those obtained in experiment (2) above, and those with two moles of aluminium chloride, identical with the results obtained in experiment (3) above.

With a view to reducing the number of steps in the synthesis of 2-acetylresorcinol the acetylation of β -resorcylic acid was studied under similar conditions, but the results have not been encouraging. On acetylation with one mole of acetic anhydride in presence of two moles of aluminium chloride, a mixture of 2-acetylresorcinol, 2:4-dihydroxy-5-acetyl- and probably -3-acetylbenzoic acids was obtained, from which 2-acetylresorcinol was obtained in poor yield. With three moles of aluminium chloride the 2:4-dihydroxy-5-acetylbenzoic acid was obtained in good yield but 2-acetylresorcinol was obtained in negligible quantity. The 2:4-dihydroxy-3-acetylbenzoic acid could not be obtained pure from the mixture in either of the experiments, only the corresponding β -isomer could be isolated in a pure state.

The formation of the γ -isomer in the Friedel and Crafts acetylation of methyl β -resorcyate is expected, though not observed so far, for methyl β -resorcyate gives the 3-formyl derivative in the Gattermann reaction (Shah and Laiwalla, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 1828) and the 5-hydroxycoumarin derivative as the main product in the Pechmann reaction with ethyl acetoacetate in presence of aluminium chloride (Sethna, Shah and Shah, *ibid.*, 1938, 228).

Having studied the acetylation of methyl β -resorcyate it was thought of interest to study the acetylation of resacetophenone under similar conditions, Desai and

Ekblas (*loc. cit.*) have carried out the Friedel and Crafts acetylation of resacetophenone and with one mole of resacetophenone, one mole of acetic anhydride and 2.2 moles of aluminium chloride they obtained a mixture containing equal parts of 2:4- and 4:6-diacetylresorcinols (1.5 g. of each from 7.5 g. resacetophenone) which was separated into its constituents by fractional crystallisation. The acetylation was carried out in the present work with (A) one mole of acetic anhydride and two moles of aluminium

TABLE I

Substance	Acetylating agent.	Aluminium chloride.	†Crude product with approx. melting range.	Pure γ -isomer.	Pure β -isomer.	Residue in the flask with approx. melting range.
Methyl- β -resorcyate	Acetic anhydride					
1 mol. (8.4 g.)	1 mol. (5.1 g.)	1 mol. (6.7 g.)	0.2 g.	—	—	Methyl β -resorcyate (4 g.)
"	"	2 mols. (13.4 g.)	2.4 g. (60-90*)	0.7 g.	0.9 g.	Pasty mass; could not be crystallised.
"	"	3 mols. (20.2 g.)	4.5 g. (70-105*)	0.8	2.7	1.3 g. (100-110*) gave 0.6 g. of pure β -isomer on crystallisation.*
"	2 mols. (10.2 g.)	"	2 g. (75-80*)	1.3	Could not be isolated	6 g. (100-110*) gave 4 g. of pure diacetyl compound on crystallisation, m.p. 112-113°.
"	Acetyl chloride					
"	1 mol. (4 g.)	1 mol. (6.7 g.)	2.4 g. (60-90*)	0.6	Not isolated	Not worked up
"	"	2 mols. (13.4 g.)	4.5 g. (70-105*)	0.7	2.1 g.	Do
β -Resorcylic acid	Acetic anhydride					
1 mol. (7.8 g.)	1 mol. (5.1 g.)	2 mols. (13.4 g.)	—	Could not be isolated	0.7	Residue (1.5 g.); 0.2 g. of 2-acetylresorcinol isolated.
"	"	3 mols. (20.2 g.)	—	Do	4.0	Residue (5 g.); 2-acetylresorcinol negligible.
Resacetophenone	Acetic anhydride					
1 mol. (7.6 g.)	1 mol. (5.1 g.)	2 mols. (13.4 g.)	3.8 g. (75-83*)	2.5 g.	Could not be isolated	3.2 g. (117-125°); crystallisation from benzene gave a small quantity of pure 4:6-diacetylresorcinol.
"	"	3 mols. (20.2 g.)	4.7 g. (82-90*-150*)	2.5	1.1 g.	2 g. (160-175°). Repeated crystallisations from benzene did not raise the m.p.
"	2 mols. (10.2 g.)	"	2.6 g. (75-80*)	1.8	Could not be isolated	7 g. (134-135°). Pure 2:4:6-triacetylresorcinol obtained by crystallisation from alcohol (6 g., m.p. 137-38°).

† From steam distillation and nitrobenzene

* In one experiment the residue was found to contain considerable amount of acid, formed probably as a result of hydrolysis of the ester during steam distillation.

chloride; (B) one mole of acetic anhydride and three moles of aluminium chloride, and (C) two moles of acetic anhydride and three moles of aluminium chloride. The reaction mixture was heated in a steam-bath for four hours. When the reaction mixture was subjected to steam distillation the 2 : 4-diacetylresorcinol first distilled over with a small quantity of 4 : 6-diacetylresorcinol. When the former had distilled over completely the latter continued to distil slowly. When the solid deposited in the condenser no longer melted on stopping the flow of water in the condenser the distillation was stopped, as this indicated that almost the whole of the 2 : 4-diacetylresorcinol had distilled over. The 2 : 4- and 4 : 6-isomers were separated by fractional crystallisation from benzene, for whereas the 2 : 4-isomer is very soluble in benzene (1 part in 10 parts of benzene at 15°) the 4 : 6-isomer is sparingly soluble (1 part in 125 parts of benzene at 15°) (Baker, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 1684).

In both the experiments, (A) and (B), the 2 : 4-diacetylresorcinol is formed in good yield. The isomeric 4 : 6-diacetylresorcinol is formed in much greater quantity in (B) than in (A). In experiment (C), in addition to these two, the 2 : 4 : 6-triacetylresorcinol is formed in excellent yield. This does not steam-distil. Limaye (*Rasayanam*, 1943, 1, 246; *C. A.*, 1944, 38, 4258) prepared 2 : 4 : 6-triacetylresorcinol by the acetylation of 4 : 6-diacetylresorcinol with acetyl chloride in presence of aluminium chloride.

Baker (*loc. cit.*) on Fries migration of 4-*O*-acetylresacetophenone obtained a mixture of 2 : 4- and 4 : 6-diacetylresorcinols from which he isolated the former by an elaborate procedure.

The work described here affords convenient methods for the preparation of 2-acetylresorcinol and 2 : 4-diacetylresorcinol.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The results obtained in the present work are shown in Table I. A few typical experiments are described in detail to illustrate the experimental procedures followed.

Acetylation of Methyl β -Resorcyate : Methyl 2:4-Dihydroxy-3-acetylbenzoate

(1) *Reaction with one mole of Acetic Anhydride and two moles of Aluminium Chloride.*—Methyl β -resorcyate (8.4 g.) and acetic anhydride (5.1 g.) were dissolved in nitrobenzene (20 c.c.) and anhydrous aluminium chloride (13.4 g.) in nitrobenzene (60 c.c.) added gradually with constant shaking. The reaction mixture was heated on a steam-bath for 4 hours. The unreacted aluminium chloride was then decomposed with ice-cold dilute hydrochloric acid and the nitrobenzene steam distilled. Steam distillation was continued further when a solid product was obtained. This was mixed with the product obtained from the steam-distilled nitrobenzene by extraction with alkali and dried (2.4 g., melting range 60°-90°). The dried material was well shaken with hexane (25 c.c.) in cold and filtered. The insoluble portion was crystallised from alcohol in stout needles (0.9 g.), m.p. 123-24°. This was methyl 2:4-dihydroxy-5-acetylbenzoate. On hydrolysis by keeping in contact with 10% sodium hydroxide the corresponding acid was obtained, m.p. 254-55°. Desai and Ekhlal (*loc. cit.*) give m.p. 124° and 256° for the ester and the acid respectively. The product obtained on removal of hexane was crystallised from alcohol in long wooly needles (0.7 g.), m.p. 83-84°. This was methyl 2:4-dihydroxy-3-

acetylbenzoate. (Found : C, 57.5; H, 5.1. $C_{10}H_{10}O_5$ requires C, 57.2; H, 4.8 per cent).

Petroleum ether (b.p. 40° - 60°) when substituted for hexane gave identical results.

The residue in the flask after steam-distillation was pasty and could not be crystallised and it was rejected.

(2) *Reaction with one mole of acetic anhydride and three moles of aluminium chloride* was carried out similarly.

(3) *Reaction with two moles of acetic anhydride and three moles of aluminium chloride* was carried out as before. In this case the product from steam distillation and nitrobenzene (2 g., melting range 75° - 82°) on repeated crystallisations from rectified spirit directly gave the γ -isomer (1.3 g., m. p. 80 - 82°). The residue in the flask (6 g., melting range 100° - 110°) gave from alcohol tiny needles (4 g.), m.p. 112 - 113° . This was methyl 2:4-dihydroxy-3:5-diacetylbenzoate, for it gave the corresponding acid, m.p. 174 - 75° , on hydrolysis by keeping in contact with 10% sodium hydroxide for 24 hours. Desai and Radha (*loc.cit.*) give m. p. 113° and 175° for the ester and the acid respectively.

(4) *Reactions with one mole of acetyl chloride and one and two moles of aluminium chloride* were carried out as in (1) above.

The 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone of methyl 2:4-dihydroxy-3-acetylbenzoate, prepared as usual, was crystallised from glacial acetic acid in tiny yellow needles, m.p. 230 - 32° . (Found : N, 14.5. $C_{16}H_{14}O_8N_4$ requires N, 14.4 per cent).

2:4-Dihydroxy-3-acetylbenzoic Acid.—Methyl 2:4-dihydroxy-3-acetylbenzoate (1 g.) was dissolved in sodium hydroxide solution (10%, 25 c.c.) and kept for 24 hours. On acidification, white amorphous mass separated which was treated with sodium bicarbonate solution to separate the acid from the unhydrolysed and decarboxylated products if any. The product obtained on acidification of the sodium bicarbonate solution crystallised from glacial acetic acid in tiny needles (0.65 g.), m.p. 195 - 96° (efferv.). (Found : C, 55.0; H, 3.9. $C_9H_8O_5$ requires C, 55.1; H, 4.1 per cent).

The 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone of the acid, prepared as usual, was crystallised from glacial acetic acid in tiny yellow needles, m.p. 264 - 66° . (Found : N, 15.1. $C_{13}H_{12}O_8N_4$ requires N, 14.9 per cent).

*Carboxylation of 2-Acetylresorcinol to 2:4-Dihydroxy-3-acetylbenzoic Acid.**—2-Acetylresorcinol (10 g.) was thoroughly mixed with potassium bicarbonate (20 g.) and glycerine (40 g.) and heated in an oil-bath in a current of carbon dioxide at 100° - 105° for six hours when a red viscous solution was obtained. This was diluted with water (150 c.c.) and acidified with concentrated hydrochloric acid. The yellow solid obtained was filtered, washed with water and treated with sodium bicarbonate solution (10%). The portion which dissolved was filtered off from the unchanged 2-acetylresorcinol and the filtrate acidified with hydrochloric acid. The product obtained was crystallised from glacial acetic acid in tiny needles (3 g.), m.p. 195 - 96° (efferv.). Mixed m.p. with the acid obtained above from hydrolysis of the ester was not depressed.

Simultaneous Hydrolysis and Decarboxylation of Methyl 2:4-Dihydroxy-3-acetylbenzoate to 2-Acetylresorcinol.—Methyl 2:4-dihydroxy-3-acetylbenzoate (1 g.) was

*First carried out by Parekh and Shah in these laboratories (unpublished work).

dissolved in sodium hydroxide solution (5%, 20 c.c.) and heated on a steam-bath for 3 hours. On acidification, a yellow mass separated which was washed with sodium bicarbonate solution to remove the intermediate acid. This was found to be negligible. The residue was crystallised from dilute alcohol in very tiny yellow crystals (0.5 g.), m.p. 155-56°. Mixed m.p. with an authentic specimen of 2-acetylresorcinol was not depressed.

The mixture obtained in (1) above (melting range 60°-90°; 1.2 g.) was heated with sodium hydroxide (5%, 24 c.c.) on a boiling water-bath for three hours and acidified with hydrochloric acid. The product obtained was treated with sodium bicarbonate solution. The portion insoluble in it was 2-acetylresorcinol (0.25 g.), m.p. and mixed m.p. 154-55°. The sodium bicarbonate filtrate was acidified with hydrochloric acid; the solid obtained (0.2 g.) gave m.p. 253° (efferv.). Mixed m.p. with 2:4-dihydroxy-5-acetylbenzoic acid was not depressed.

Acetylation of β -Resorcylic Acid.— β -Resorcylic acid was acetylated with one mole of acetic anhydride in presence of two moles of aluminium chloride as in (1) above and the reaction mixture worked up as before. No product distilled with steam. The residue in the flask was filtered and treated with sodium bicarbonate solution. The insoluble portion (0.2 g.) was 2-acetylresorcinol as seen from m.p. and mixed m.p. The sodium bicarbonate solution was acidified. The product obtained was crystallised from rectified spirit in tiny crystals (0.7 g.) m.p. 255° (efferv.). Mixed m.p. with 2:4-dihydroxy-5-acetylbenzoic acid obtained above was not depressed. The mother-liquor on evaporation gave a product melting with considerable range and did not give any pure product on further crystallisation or fractionation with alcohol or benzene.

When the experiment was carried out with 3 moles of aluminium chloride the 2-acetylresorcinol was obtained in negligible quantity but the 2:4-dihydroxy-5-acetylbenzoic was obtained in good yield (4 g.). From the mother-liquor no other pure product could be isolated.

Acetylation of Resacetophenone

(A). *Reaction with One mole of Acetic Anhydride and Two moles of Aluminium Chloride.*—Resacetophenone (7.5 g.) and acetic anhydride (5.1 g.) were dissolved in nitrobenzene (20 c.c.) and a solution of aluminium chloride (13.4 g.) in nitrobenzene (60 c.c.) added gradually with shaking. The reaction was vigorous and considerable heat was evolved. The reaction mixture was heated on a steam-bath for 4 hours. On cooling, the reaction mixture was treated with cold dilute hydrochloric acid and steam distilled. After the nitrobenzene had steam-distilled the steam-distillation was continued further. This was stopped when the product solidifying in the condenser did not melt even when the flow of water in the condenser was stopped. The product which had steam-distilled was collected and mixed with the product obtained from nitrobenzene by extraction with dilute alkali. (Total yield 3.8 g., m. range, 75°-83°). This on repeated crystallisations from alcohol gave a product (2.5 g., m.p. 85-87°). This was 2:4-diacetylresorcinol. [Desai and Eklhas (*loc. cit.*) give m.p. 85-86°; Desai and Radha (*loc. cit.*) give m.p. 95-96°; Baker (*loc. cit.*) gives m.p. 85-87°]. The residue (3.2 g.) in the flask which was dark brown in colour and slightly pasty, on crystallisation from

rectified spirit gave an impure product of m. range 117° - 125° . On crystallisation from benzene a small quantity of 4:6-diacetylresorcinol, m.p. 182° was obtained. Desai and Ekhlis (*loc. cit.*) give m.p. 185° and Baker (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934; 71) gives m.p. 182° for 4:6-diacetylresorcinol.

If the 2:4-diacetylresorcinol is contaminated with considerable quantity of 4:6-diacetylresorcinol and cannot be purified by crystallisation, the method of fractionation with benzene as given below in (B) may be followed.

(B). In the reaction with one mole of acetic anhydride and three moles of aluminium chloride the product obtained on steam-distillation on crystallisation from alcohol did not give the pure 2:4-diacetylresorcinol; so it was subjected to fractionation with benzene. The whole of the product (4.7 g.) was dissolved in about 30 c.c. of hot benzene and cooled. The stout needles which separated had m. range, 168° - 175° . This on recrystallisation from alcohol gave the pure 4:6-diacetylresorcinol (1.1 g.), m.p. 182° . The product obtained on evaporation of benzene was crystallised from alcohol when the pure 2:4-diacetylresorcinol was obtained as long wooly needles (2.5 g.), m.p. 85 - 87° . The dark brown residue remaining in the flask after steam distillation (2 g., m. range 160° - 175°) could not be purified by crystallisation or fractionation with benzene.

(C). In the reaction with two moles of acetic anhydride and three moles of aluminium chloride the product from steam distillation (2.6 g., m. range 75 - 80°) did not give a pure product on crystallisation from rectified spirit and was therefore shaken with cold petroleum ether (30 c.c., b.p. 40° - 60°). The portion which did not dissolve melted with a range. The product obtained on removal of petroleum ether gave m.p. 83 - 85° , yield 1.8 g.

The brownish residue in the flask (7 g., m.p. 134 - 35°) was crystallised from alcohol when long pinkish needles (6 g.), m.p. 137 - 38° were obtained. Its mixed m.p. with resacetophenone was lowered by over 20° . It was obtained unchanged after keeping overnight with 10% sodium hydroxide. (Found: C, 60.7; H, 5.0. Calc. for $C_{12}H_{12}O_2$: C, 61.0; H, 5.1 per cent). It was therefore 2:4:6-triacetylresorcinol. Limaye (*loc. cit.*) gives m.p. 136° . The 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone, prepared as usual, was crystallised from acetic acid in tiny needles, m.p. 262 - 63° . (Found: N, 13.8. $C_{18}H_{16}O_8N_4$ requires N, 13.4 per cent). There was no appreciable change in the yields of the products when the acetylations were carried out at 120° - 125° .

Further work on the Friedel and Crafts acylation of methyl β -resorcyate is in progress.

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